

Training Needs for Head-Teachers in Management of Ecde Curriculum Implementation in Primary Schools in Marakwet District, Kenya

Author Details:

Chepkonga C. Mildred, Department of CIEM, Moi University, mchebet65@gmail.com

Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to investigate the training needs of primary school head-teachers in the management of early childhood development education curriculum implementation in Marakwet district of Rift Valley province. The study was guided by the needs assessment process as defined by English and Kaufman. Descriptive survey research design was used in conducting the study since the design enables gathering of data at a particular point in time with the intention of describing the nature of the existing conditions, identifying the standards against which existing conditions can be compared and determining the relationship that exists between specific events (Orodho, 2005). The respondents were the quality assurance and standards officers (QASOs), Primary school head-teachers, deputy head-teachers and teachers of ECDE. The selection of the study sample was done using simple random sampling, stratified random sampling and purposive sampling. Schools were stratified into educational divisions from which 38 schools out of the total of 97 were proportionately sampled from the district. To obtain the specific schools to participate in the study, simple random sampling was used. All head-teachers and deputy head-teachers from the selected schools were purposively sampled for inclusion in the study. Seventy six out of the total 198 ECDE teachers were selected through simple random sampling while all the 10 QASOs in the district were purposively sampled. The questionnaire, document analysis and an interview schedule were used to collect data for this study. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies, means, standard deviations and percentages. Presentation was done using tables, graphs and charts. The findings of this study revealed that there were various factors that influence the implementation of the ECDE curriculum such as supervision of teachers and teaching/learning resources. It was also observed that the head-teachers utilized various competencies while managing the ECDE curriculum implementation process. There also existed a gap between what should be, and what was in all the macro-competencies studied regarding the training needs of primary school head-teachers in their capacities as managers of the ECDE curriculum implementation process. The study recommended that the government through the Ministry of Education should train primary school teachers in management of the ECDE curriculum and the colleges preparing teachers in ECDE should introduce courses specifically addressing ECDE curriculum management.

Keywords: Primary schools, Teacher's Trainings

Introduction

Curriculum implementation is one area in which the head- teacher should be familiar with to ensure effective implementation (Callander, 1961). In this context, it is the head- teacher's responsibility to supervise the extent to which activities of teachers, children and parents are fulfilling to meet the demands of curriculum implementation (Olembo, Wanga & Karagu, 1992), making him/her accountable and responsible for effecting preschool goals (Okumbe, 1998).

The world conference on Education For All (EFA) that took place in Jomtein, Thailand (March 1990) articulated the significance of early years as foundation for life of an individual. This need to be addressed through implementing the present ECDE curriculum by teachers concerned for enhancement of holistic development in children. According to recent research on brain development emphasize that the first six years of life are extremely important, the environment experiences during this period are significant. At six years, the child's brain is 90% of its adult weight and size. All connection will have been developed (Rima, 1997). In ECDE there is need to 'maximize' what the curriculum requires for holistic development of children at the age of six years (World Conference on Education for all 1990).

School head-teachers are thus the immediate supervisors or inspectors of their schools who should ensure the smooth running of the school. Performance in most schools in Kenya has remained poor for quite sometime. In

a report by the Ministry of Education cited in the Standard Newspaper Media Group of Thursday 7th May 2009, poor or lack of supervision, laxity among school teachers, lack of schemes of work, records of work covered and lesson plans were cited as some of the reasons for the dismal performance in Marakwet District and Kenya at large.

Daresh and Playko (1995) argue that school head-teachers ought to be equipped with the necessary skills to enable them deal with situations and problems comprehensively as they arise. These authorities argue that the practice of supervision dates back to the history of formal education in American schools during the 17th century. In 1642 the first Massachusetts school of law marked the beginning of educational supervision in American schools. During this period supervisors were primarily engaged in inspection, an approach based on the assumption that an educational supervisor's job was to find out all the wrong things that teachers were doing in their classrooms. However with time the role of supervisors has changed from fault-finding to peer counseling or remedial coaching (Koech Commission 1999)

Kitavi (1997) observes that pre-service training of school teachers in Kenya, does not adequately address the aspects of ECDE curriculum implementation supervision. School head-teachers thus continue to face problems due to lack of the necessary skills to be used in curriculum supervision. This is an indication that head-teachers are not adequately equipped with sufficient management skills more especially in the area of educational supervision (Kafu,1976). Given the above background, this study intended to establish the training needs of Primary school head-teachers in ECDE curriculum supervision.

Problem formulation

Research in Kenya indicates that poor background in pre-school is a major set-back in education as it was indicated by the Ministry of Education that class repetition is associated with inefficiency and inequity in the provision of education (UNICEF Report, 2007). As a result, the Minister of Education elaborated that the "results have taken stock of our achievement in implementing the curriculum and factors that affect it." There are a number of factors that influence curriculum implementation. The role of curriculum developers and other education stakeholders is to be aware of the sources and influences of the factors. This is because effective ECDE curriculum implementation needs a synthesis of the factors that influence the experiences that children are supposed to go through under the teacher's guidance (Caswel, 1995).

Due to the changes made in objectives, content and teaching approaches, ECDE curriculum requires necessary conditions to be fulfilled. One such condition is the training of the teaching staff on new trends in pedagogy. These thus may include retraining and in-servicing of teachers to acquire knowledge, skills and attitudes. It also should include availability and use of instructional resources, sufficient administrative support and use of the right teaching methods.

Of special interest however is whether the head teachers are aware of the tasks they ought to undertake for teachers, children and parents towards the implementation of preschool curriculum. Research indicates that that head teachers have little to do with the implementation of preschool curriculum (Abere, 2006). Therefore, there was need to investigate the training needs of primary school head-teachers in the management of ECDE curriculum implementation.

- i. To identify the factors that influence the implementation of ECDE curriculum*
- ii. To examine the head-teachers' instructional management practices of the ECDE curriculum implementation*

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is based on the needs assessment process. **Witkin and Altschuld (1991)** define needs assessment as a tool which formally identifies the gaps between the current results or outcomes/products and required or desired results, places these gaps in priority and selects those gaps/needs of the highest priority for action, usually through the implementation of a new or existing curriculum or management process. Suarez (1991) further define needs assessment as an information gathering and analyzing process in the identification of the needs of individuals, groups, institutions and communities or societies.

The point to be noted here is that, curriculum development requires systematic and specific procedures to be followed. Various authors have proposed various curriculum development models. However it is important to note that despite the fact, there exist these various curriculum development models. All curriculum scholars agree on the fact that whether developing a new curriculum or changing the existing one, the process begins with needs assessment.

It can be argued that any education system in any given society, helps enhance the society's needs and therefore, in drawing an educational program, a needs assessment is imperative. The needs assessment allows for a careful investigation of what should be, and what is, so as to establish the discrepancy. This discrepancy model can be expressed in mathematical terms as follows:

$$\boxed{\text{What should be (desired)}} - \boxed{\text{What is (actual)}} = \boxed{\text{Need/Gap/Discrepancy}}$$

The needs of school head-teachers as educational leaders keep on changing from time to time, which necessitated this assessment process so as to establish competencies that they require in order to effectively manage the ECDE curriculum implementation in their schools.

Literature Review

Pre-School Curriculum

With the developments that had taken place in ECE after the Gachathi Report (1976), specifically the formation of NACECE and DICECEs, the curriculum allowed discretion for the teacher to make decisions on a variety of contextual factors, but basically it included;

- Language development and pre-literacy skills
- Mathematics (pre-number) activities
- Environmental activities which included social and pre-science activities
- Creative activities which included art and crafts, music, outdoor play and physical activities (MOEST, 1987).

This current pre-school curriculum for children between 3 – 6 years in Kenya has been developed with regard to the children's developmental stages. It is activity-based similar to that of traditional African education in its emphasis of language development, environmental awareness, number work, music, movement, art, craft, physical development, religions and moral education, general health, nutrition and childcare (Woolman, 2001).

Pre-school curriculum has gained focus from the government through the Ministry of Education in the recent past. The National centre for Early Childhood Education (NACECE) and the District centres for Early Childhood Education (DICECEs) are currently very active points at which early childhood curriculum is receiving deliberate recast (Otunga, 2010). There are many activities, workshops and in-service training sessions being undertaken for those involved in this phase of education, all focused on qualitative improvement of curriculum and human resource development for this level education of education. On curriculum and human resources development for this level of education. On the issue of human resource development, universities

specifically Kenyatta University and Moi University have implemented degree programmes in early childhood education within the faculties and schools of education (Otunga, 2010).

2.8. Teacher Competency and Training

Hewton (1988) says that competency refers to appropriate prior knowledge, skills, attitudes, and abilities in a given context that adjust and develop with time and needs in order to effectively and efficiently accomplish a task and that are measured against a minimum standard. Hewton (1988) further lists the following as Characteristics of Teacher Competencies:

2.8.1 Content Area Knowledge

In addition to a mastery of basic skills, effective teachers are expected to demonstrate a thorough understanding of the content of their curricular areas. They should be able to communicate this content material to students using methodologies that are appropriate for the age and abilities of the learners. These teachers are competent planners, seek to incorporate other disciplines into their lessons and stay abreast of changes and advancements in their specialty areas.

2.8.2 Pedagogical Capabilities

Successful teachers are knowledgeable about multiple methods of instruction. They understand levels of human development, both typical and atypical, and should be able to diversify their lessons to meet the needs of learners of all ability levels. These teachers are capable classroom managers and skilled at motivating students, and they perennially assess both student and personal achievement.

2.8.3 Communication Skills

Not only should teachers exhibit the skills necessary for communicating ideas clearly to students, but they must also communicate with parents, other teachers, their administrators and their communities. They must be open, approachable and diplomatic in conveying information. In a technologically oriented world, these teachers will use contemporary modes of communication like email and interactive websites in addition to traditional means of communication.

2.8.4 Professionalism

Teacher excellence is reflected in a professional's efforts toward continual improvement in his field. Professional teachers are marked by their personal presentation, reflection, collaboration, the desire to advance and adaptability. These teachers believe students can learn, understand the value of diversity in the workplace and in their classrooms, and understand the ethical implications of working with students. Recent studies in Kenya (Mohammed 1994, Karimi. 1993, ASSP 1993, Mbugua 1987) found out that, despite the fact that official course syllabuses demand an integrated approach in the teaching of GHC course, actual classroom practice in the college still follows the separate subject approach. This disparity is quite obvious. But at the same time the application of this disparity is much more serious than it appears on the surface. What this means is that because the training in the colleges follows this separate teaching of Geography, History, and Civics, one of the most important elements of GHC, integrated approach, which makes this subject essentially different from what it replaced, remains totally unattended at the training stage. This therefore means that the major gap is already in the head-teachers' knowledge and understanding as far as supervision of ECDE curriculum is concerned.

Much has been written about the role of teachers and their training in any educational change undertaking. All agree that teachers are central to change process and therefore their training is quite crucial. Verspoor, (1989:2)

asserts that a well-designed and effectively implemented teacher-training programme is the key element in the successful implementation and institutionalization of change programmes. It thus follows that any successful educational change is built on effective teacher training. By comparison, another research report of World Bank on education in fourteen countries attributed failure of intended educational change mainly to ineffective teacher training programmes (Kallagan & Greany, 1992:29)

Material and methods

This study used descriptive survey design. All primary school head-teachers, quality assurance and standards officers, deputy head-teachers and teachers of early childhood education comprised the target population. Seventy six out of the total 198 ECDE teachers were selected through simple random sampling while all the 10 QASOs in the district were purposively sampled. The total number of respondents (162) constituted over 30% of the target population which is an adequate sample size (Kerlinger 1986). The main research instrument for this study was the questionnaire. Interview schedule was also used by the researcher to overcome the limitations of the questionnaire. In this study, the researcher tested the reliability of the research instruments through the test-retest method. Spearman rank order correlation was used to compute the reliability at ± 0.5 level of significance. A correlation coefficient of 0.7 was obtained and therefore considered good enough, as advocated by Orodho (2005). In this study, descriptive statistical techniques were used. The descriptive statistical techniques used in this study included the frequencies, percentages, standard deviation and means.

Findings and Discussion

This section presents the results of the present study as obtained from the analysis of the collected data from the study whose main objective was to investigate the ECDE curriculum management training needs of primary school head-teachers.

Sample Characteristics

One of the characteristics of the respondents regarding their background that was captured in this study was sex. 36 (31.6%) out of the total of 114 respondents were male while the rest 78 (68.4%) were females. It is important to note here that in the Kenyan context, the teaching force at ECDE level is still dominated by female teachers. This is the trend that is reflected in these findings in which the female teachers were found to be more as compared to the male teachers. This indicated a great gender disparity in the teaching force in the district at this level, an issue that will need to be addressed. It is observed that the item that sought information on the current responsibilities of the respondents had two options, namely; deputy head-teachers and class teachers. It is evident that majority (31.6%) of the respondents were young teachers aged below 30 years. Those aged over 35 years constituted the minority, implying that teachers at this level are relatively young in the teaching profession or fresh graduates from colleges. The information on age was included in this study because Mullei (1985) posits that age determines the choice of teaching methods to be used. He argues that young ECDE teachers may find themselves in a dilemma especially where they have never dealt with children before. Findings reveal that 100% of the respondents were academically qualified to execute duties assigned to them in their current positions. This is because for one to teach at ECDE level, he/she should possess minimum academic qualification of a certificate in ECDE, while for one to teach at primary level, he/she should have a P1 certificate. It is evidently clear that majority 42 (36.8%) of the respondents have little experience. This confirms an earlier finding that most of the teachers in ECDE are fresh graduates from college. This perhaps explains the need to have permanent staff at this level of education so as to have teachers staying longer in the profession in order to gain the required experience.

4.3 Factors That Influence the Implementation of ECDE Curriculum

This study investigated the various factors that influence the implementation of ECDE Curriculum. These factors included: learning resources, QASO supervision, supervision by head-teachers, experience in teaching, training of teachers.

Table 4.5: Teaching Experience

Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percent
less than 3 years	42	36.8
4 to 6 years	24	21.1
7 to 9 years	12	10.5
above 10 years	36	31.6
Total	114	100.0

4.3.1 Adequacy of Learning Resources

The importance of learning resources in the learning process can not be overemphasized. This study investigated whether the learning resources affected the learning process in ECDE centres. The findings are as shown in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 shows that majority, 78 (68.4%), strongly agreed that inadequate learning resources affected the implementation of curriculum in the ECDE centres. The rest (31.6%) agreed that inadequate learning resources was a factor that influenced the implementation of curriculum in ECDE centres.

The study, therefore, found out that 100 % of respondents indicated that the learning resources influence the implementation of ECDE curriculum. The unanimous agreement of the respondents that learning resources influence the implementation of the ECDE curriculum emphasizes the invaluable importance of the resources in instruction as established by Kafu (1976).

4.3.2 QASO Supervision

This study investigated whether inadequate QASO supervision hindered effective implementation of curriculum. The findings are as shown in figure 4.2. The figure shows that 90(79%) out of the total 114 of the respondents agreed that QASO supervision affected the process of curriculum implementation in ECDE's in the district.

The table further shows that 18 (15.8%) disagreed with this, while the rest 6 (5.2%) were undecided. The high number of respondents reporting that QASO supervision affected the process of curriculum implementation in ECDE's implies that indeed supervision is critical in curriculum implementation since it plays a major role in creating positive relationship between head teachers, teachers and students. Supervisors also give guidance to the school members on various school matters such as curriculum implementation (Bulin, 1997).

Fig 4.1: Adequacy of Learning Resources

4.3.3 Supervision by Head-teachers

The supervision done by the school head-teacher in the curriculum implementation was investigated by this study to determine whether it influences the process. It was felt necessary to do this since in a school set up, the head-teacher has the overall responsibility over the operation of the school. His/her responsibility in this

respect, involves the interpretation of educational policies and objectives as well as implementation of the curriculum. His/her roles are thus those of instructional leadership, administration and supervision (Ngala, 1997). The findings on this aspect are as shown in Figure 4.3

The figure shows that 54 (47.4%) of the total 114 respondents agreed that the supervision done by head-teachers influences ECDE curriculum implementation. The figure further shows that another 54 (47.4%) of the total 114 respondents disagreed that the supervision done by head-teachers influences ECDE curriculum implementation. The rest, 6 (5.2%), were undecided. This finding may not favour a firm conclusion that the supervision by head-teacher influence or does not influence ECDE curriculum implementation. This perhaps explains the need to have head-teachers acquire

ECDE supervision skills so as to be better positioned to exert their influence in the supervision of ECDE activities.

It is observed that the supervision done by both the head-teacher and the QASOs is crucial in curriculum implementation. Ngala (1997) observes that the head-teacher has to be effective in influencing teacher's perception of work, while the QASOS should assist teachers in their work rather than engage in fault finding. He argues that if the QASOs play their roles effectively, the productivity in terms of academic performance can be greatly improved.

4.3.4 Experience in Teaching

The experience in teaching of the respondents was investigated by this study. The study sought to establish whether the experience in teaching affected the effective implementation of ECDE curriculum. The findings are as shown in Figure 4.4.

The figure shows that the majority 66 (57.9%) out of the total of 114 respondents agreed that the experience in teaching affected the implementation of the ECDE curriculum. The table further shows that 42 (36.9 %) out of the total of 114 respondents disagreed that experience in teaching affected the implementation of the ECDE curriculum. The rest, 6 (5.2%), were undecided. Experience in the world of work is critical and its importance can not be overemphasized since an experienced staff is better placed to deliver better results as compared to the inexperienced. The reason perhaps why, majority were in favour of experience as a factor influencing curriculum implementation. It is also important to observe that teaching experience provides a variety of experiences to teachers in terms of years and exposures. It also determines the quantity and quality of competences a teacher has. Teachers who are more experienced in early childhood development education have positive relationships with their ECDE children as compared to those colleagues who are less experienced (Gakii, 2003).

4.3.5 Training of Teachers

The training of teachers in the district was investigated to establish whether it affected the effective implementation of ECDE curriculum. The findings are as shown in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.2 QASO Supervision

Figure 4.3: Supervision by Head-teachers

The figure shows that majority 84, (73.7 %), out of the total of 114 respondents agreed that training of teachers in the district affected the implementation of ECDE curriculum.

Twenty one point one (21.1%) respondents disagreed that training of teachers affects the implementation of ECDE curriculum. The rest, 6 (5.2%) respondents were undecided on whether training of teachers affects the implementation of ECDE curriculum. The overwhelming majority, who expressed their view that training of teachers is a factor that influences curriculum implementation, stresses the importance of teacher training as a significant ingredient in effective implementation of curriculum. It is also important to observe that continuous training is necessary so as to keep the teachers updated. In addition, the needs assessment theory that guided this study is defined as a tool which formally identifies the gaps between the current results or outcomes/products and required or desired results, places these gaps in priority and selects those gaps/needs of the highest priority for action, usually through the implementation of a new or existing curriculum or management process (English and Kaufman, 1975). It will thus be of significant importance in identifying the teachers' training needs in ECDE curriculum management.

4.4 Head-Teachers' Instructional Management Practices

This study investigated various head-teachers' instructional management practices utilized in the implementation of the ECDE curriculum. The practices investigated were grouped into eight main head-teacher competencies that were considered core in the management of the ECDE curriculum implementation process. These consisted of planning and coordination, communication, curriculum instruction, motivation, public relations, financial management, staff development and appraisal. They were, therefore, presented for rating and the respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which it is desirable to acquire and practice the competencies and the extent to which in their experience, Primary school head-teachers actually demonstrate these competencies while managing the ECDE curriculum implementation process.

Figure 4.4: Teachers' Experience on Implementation of ECDE curriculum

Figure 4.5: Training of Teachers

It is important to observe that in analyzing these practices, the 5-point Likert scale (strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree) used in this study was collapsed into three. That is, agree undecided and disagree.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

Basing on the study objectives, it was concluded that there are various factors that influence the management of the ECDE curriculum implementation process. These include adequacy of learning resources, quality assurance and standards officers' supervision, supervision by head-teachers, teachers' experience and the teacher's training. Another conclusion made from the analysis of the study findings is that primary school head-teachers utilize various competencies in the management of ECDE curriculum. These competencies are policy formulation, motivation, communication and staff development. It can also be concluded that from the assessment of competencies studied, the current practice is inadequate. This is because for all the competencies, there exists a discrepancy (gap) between the current practice and the desired practice. This therefore implies

that if the head-teachers are to be trained in ECDE curriculum management, then this training should include all relevant competencies.

Recommendations

This study clearly underscores the importance of ECDE in Marakwet district. On the basis of the information gathered, the researcher observed that further efforts were necessary to further improve the effectiveness ECDE curriculum management in meeting the children's expectations. As a result therefore, the following recommendations were made:

- i) The government through the Ministry of Education should train primary school teachers in management of the ECDE curriculum. This is because ECDE extends to standard three, and the primary school teachers in their initial training that is offered in primary teacher training colleges does not address issues pertaining to ECDE.
- ii) The colleges preparing teachers in ECDE should introduce courses specifically addressing ECDE curriculum management
- iii) The government through the Ministry of Education should introduce in primary teacher training colleges courses in ECDE curriculum management
- iv) The quality assurance and standards officers who are charged with the responsibility of supervising educational activities in schools should be trained by Kenya Education Staff Institute in ECDE supervision.
- v) The Ministry of Education through Kenya Education Staff Institute should equip the primary school head-teachers with the relevant skills in management of ECDE curriculum.
- vi) Learning resources in ECDE centres should be improved by NACECE

It is suggested that further investigation should be conducted to establish the training needs of primary school head-teachers in other areas such as in guidance and counseling. Similar studies should also be conducted in future to establish the extent of change in the training needs over time.

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